

An Investigation of Effect of Bio-Medical Waste on Concrete

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Abstract— In India hospital bio medical waste (BMW) causing major problem. This research investigates the impact of incorporating biomedical waste (BMW) into concrete, aiming to evaluate its influence on mechanical and durability properties. Biomedical waste, posing significant environmental challenges, necessitates innovative waste management solutions. By integrating BMW into concrete, this study seeks to address both waste disposal issues and promote sustainable construction practices. The experimental approach involves varying proportions of BMW in concrete mixtures, assessing effects on parameters like compressive strength, flexural strength, permeability, and resistance to aggressive environments. Results will be compared with conventional concrete to ascertain the feasibility and potential benefits of BMW utilization in concrete production. This research contributes to environmental sustainability and civil engineering by offering insights into alternative waste management strategies and potential enhancements to concrete performance. The ultimate goal is to encourage the adoption of sustainable practices in the construction industry while tackling the complexities of biomedical waste disposal.

Keywords— Bio medical waste, Concrete, Durability, Corrosion, Microbial activity, Waste management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bio-medical waste, also referred to as hospital waste, encompasses a diverse array of materials containing infectious or potentially infectious substances. It is generated during various medical activities such as treatment, research, and veterinary care. The common producers of biomedical waste include health clinics, hospitals, laboratories, physicians, dentists, veterinarians, and providers of home healthcare services.

In India, the volume of biomedical waste generated daily is substantial, estimated at around 405,702 kilograms. Despite efforts to address this issue, approximately 72% of this waste is disposed of properly, while more than 28% remains unattended. The improper management of

biomedical waste poses significant risks to public health and the environment.

Given the hazardous nature of biomedical waste, it is crucial to prioritize its proper management and disposal. Effective strategies and protocols must be implemented to ensure the safe handling, transportation, treatment, and disposal of such waste. By doing so, we can mitigate the potential health and environmental impacts associated with biomedical waste while safeguarding communities and ecosystems

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

“Effective Utilization of Bio- Medical Waste in Construction Industry. International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology”, Uma Devi Prof. R. Rathiga

The advantages of BMW concrete is to reducing the level of Biomedical wastes and it can be effectively used in concrete making for the purpose of increase in strength and also reducing the cost

“Effect of Bio-Medical Waste on Compressive Strength of Concrete Cylinders” , Ghulam Mustafa Khanzada, Bashir Ahmed Menon, Mahboob Oad, M. F. Aijaz Khanzada, Aqib M. Lashari

Workability of concrete made using biomedical waste ash is lower than that of conventional concrete. The compressive strength of concrete decreased with addition of BMW ash when compared to conventional concrete.

“Suitability of Biomedical Waste Ash in Concrete”, Udit Kumar, Vikas Srivastava, Amit Kumar Singh

Workability of concrete made using biomedical waste ash is lower than that of conventional concrete. Density of concrete decreased slightly with increase in replacement level. However, up to 15% replacement level density was about 99% of that of conventional concrete

“Partial Replacement of Biomedical Waste ASH in Concrete”, Sathvik S, Suchith. S, Edwin Jemimahcarmich eal

Workability of concrete made using biomedical waste ash is lower than that of conventional concrete. The compressive strength of concrete decreased with addition of BMW ash when compared to conventional concrete

“Use of biomedical plastic waste in bituminous road construction”, Tina Maria Sunny, Assistant Professor

It is found that mixes prepared with biomedical plastic waste has shown better properties compared to the

Manuscript Received May 5, 2024; Revised 15 May, 2024 and Published on May 30, 2024

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conventional bituminous mixes. Hence, the biomedical plastic waste can be disposed of judiciously by incorporating it in bituminous mixes.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. compressive strength test and water Absorption test

the Indian standard which details the method of compressive strength test requiring of the machine is IS:456:2000 method of test for strength of concrete

1. Sample Preparation: Specimens are prepared according to standard specifications, usually cylindrical or cubical in shape.

2. Testing Setup The specimen is placed in a compression testing machine. The load is applied gradually until the specimen fails.

3 Measurement: The maximum load sustained by the specimen before failure is recorded. Compressive strength is calculated by dividing this load by the cross-sectional area of the specimen.

4. Reporting Results are typically reported in units of force per unit area (e.g., MPa or psi).

B. the compressive strength of the concrete cube test provides

An idea about all the characteristics of concrete. By this single test one judge the whether concreting has been done properly or not. Concrete compressive strength for generally construction varies from 15 Mpa (2200psi) to 30 Mpa (4400psi) and higher in commercial and industrial structure.

1. Quality Assessment: It assesses the quality of concrete by determining its ability to withstand compressive loads. Higher compressive strength indicates better quality concrete.

2. Design Verification: Engineers use compressive strength test results to verify if the concrete mix meets the design requirements and specifications for the intended application.

3. Durability Prediction: Compressive strength test results help predict the long-term durability of concrete structures, such as buildings, bridges, and roads, under various environmental conditions.

4. Quality Control: Contractors and construction companies use compressive strength tests for quality control purposes during construction to ensure that concrete batches meet specified strength requirements.

5. Safety Assurance: Knowing the compressive strength of concrete is crucial for ensuring the safety of structures and preventing failures due to inadequate strength.

C. Compressive strength definition

Compressive strength is the ability of a material to resist axially directed pushing forces, typically applied along the longitudinal axis of the material. It is a measure of the material's ability to withstand compression or squeezing forces without breaking or deforming permanently.

Compressive strength is usually expressed in units of force per unit area, such as MPa (megapascals) or psi (pounds per square inch). In construction materials like concrete, bricks, and stones, compressive strength is a critical parameter used to assess the material's suitability for various structural applications. ensuring the safety of structures and preventing failures due to inadequate strength.

$$\text{Compressive strength} = \text{load/cross section area}$$

Fig. 1: Waste after incineration

Fig. 2: Bio-medical waste ash

Figure 1: Bio medical waste ash

Biomedical waste ash refers to the residue left behind after the incineration of biomedical waste. Biomedical waste includes any waste that contains infectious or potentially infectious materials, such as blood, bodily fluids, or used medical supplies.

When biomedical waste is incinerated, the organic components are burned away, leaving behind ash and non-combustible residues. This ash may contain traces of heavy metals, pathogens, or other hazardous substances that were present in the original waste. Proper disposal of biomedical waste ash is crucial to prevent environmental contamination and potential health risks. Typically, specialized facilities and procedures are used to handle and dispose of biomedical waste ash safely and effectively.

2) MATERIAL USED

- Sand
- Aggregate
- Sand Aggregate
- Cement
- Water
- Fine Aggregate
- Bio-medical Waste

3)Planning Of Greywater Treatment Plant

Screening Chamber: To removed large solids particles

Activated Carbon Charcoal: To Removed Organic matter, Suspended solids, Heavy metals, Pesticides, Pharmaceuticals, Bacteria & Viruses

Filtration: To Removed suspended solids, bacteria, and viruses

Alum: It is used to removed suspended solids, organic matter, Heavy metals, less likely to react with Chlorine and improve the Quality of Water

Storage tank: To stored Treated Water

4)For Washing Purpose:

Allow the greywater to enter from the greywater inlet. Water passed from the steel strainer and entered the charcoal bed chamber, in which to close tap 1 and open tap 2 for clean water. Then clean water passes through the filtration process. Filter water enters into the alum chamber. In the alum chamber, from tap 3, clean water gets

D. We test concrete for 7 days ,14 days and 28 days

Concrete gain maximum strength at 28 days, since in construction sector great amount of capital is at stake, so instead of checking strength at 28 days we can check strength in terms of concrete strength psi at 7 days and 14 days to predict the target strength of construction work.

From the below table it is clear that, concrete gains 16% of its strength with 24 hrs, whereas concrete gains 65% of the target strength by the time of 7 days of its casting.

Till 14 days concrete show 90% of the target strength and there after the gain in strength slow down and it taken 28 days to achieve 99% of strength.

1. Initial Strength Gain: Within the first 24 hours after casting, concrete typically achieves around 16% of its target strength. This initial setting period is crucial for ensuring the stability and early strength development of the structure.

2. 7-Day Strength: By the end of the 7th day, concrete usually reaches approximately 65% of its target strength. This milestone allows for an early assessment of the concrete's strength and can inform decisions regarding formwork removal or load-bearing capabilities.

3. 14-Day Strength: At the 14-day mark, concrete typically exhibits about 90% of its target strength. This indicates significant progress in the curing process and provides confidence in the structural integrity of the construction project.

4. Steady Strength Gain: Beyond the 14-day period, the rate of strength gain slows down. However, concrete continues to gradually increase in strength, albeit at a reduced pace.

5. 28-Day Strength: It usually takes 28 days for concrete to achieve approximately 99% of its target strength. This extended curing period ensures that the concrete reaches its maximum potential strength, providing durability and longevity to the structure.

E. Procedure for testing the compressive strength of concrete cube Apparatus for Concrete Cube Test:

Compression testing machine.

2) Preparation of Concrete Cube Specimen The proportion and material for making these test specimens are from the same concrete used in the field.

3) Specimen 9 cubes Of 15cm size mix, M25.

4) Mixing of Concrete for Cube Test Mix the concrete either by hand or in a laboratory batch machine

5) Hand Mixing

Mix the concrete and fine aggregate on a watertight none-absorption platform until the mixture is thoroughly blended and is of uniform color.

Add the coarse aggregate and mix with cement and fine aggregate until the coarse aggregate is uniformly distributed throughout the batch

Add water and mix it until the concrete appears to be homogeneous and of the desired consistency.

6) Sampling of cubes for test

Clean the mounds and apply oil.

Fill the concrete in the molds in layers approximately 5cm thick.

Compare each layer with not less than 35 strokes per layer using a tamping rod (steel bar 16mm diameter and 60cm long, bullet-pointed at lower end).

Level the top surface and smoothen it with a trowel.

1. Cleaning and Oiling Molds: Before filling the molds with concrete, ensure they are clean and free from any debris. Apply a thin layer of oil to the inner surfaces of the molds to prevent the concrete from sticking and facilitate easy removal of the hardened cubes.

2. Filling the Molds: Carefully fill the molds with the prepared concrete mixture in layers approximately 5cm thick. This layering process helps ensure uniform distribution of the concrete and minimizes the risk of air voids or segregation within the cubes.

3. Compaction: After each layer of concrete is added to the mold, compact it thoroughly using a tamping rod. Apply not less than 35 strokes per layer to achieve proper compaction. The tamping rod should be a steel bar with a diameter of 16mm and a length of 60cm, with the lower end bullet-pointed for easy penetration into the concrete.

4. Leveling: Once all layers are compacted, level the top surface of the concrete using a straight edge or a trowel. Ensure the top surface is smooth and even to obtain accurate test results during compression testing.

5. Smoothing: After leveling, use a trowel to smoothen the surface of the concrete cubes. This step helps remove any excess concrete and creates a flat, uniform surface for accurate measurement and testing.

Standards and advocating for a systematic and efficient approach to water conservation in residential settings.

pH = 6.89

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Days	Conventional cubes	Bio-Medical waste add		
		15%	20%	25%
7 Days	19.21 KN	24.23 KN	24.89 KN	16.89 KN
14 Days	20.89 KN	19.12 KN	22.78 KN	16.00 KN
28 Days	20.89 KN	21.33 KN	24.89 KN	14.67 KN

Comparing Conventional cube with 15% Add Bio-Medical Waste

(a)

Comparing Conventional Cube with 20% Add Bio-Medical Waste

(b)

Comparing Conventional Cube with 25% Bio-Medical Waste

(c)

Comparing Conventional cube, 15%,20%,25% Add Bio-Medical Waste Without Replacing

(d)

1. Graph (1) shows the Compression between Conventional Concrete Cube with 15% Add Bio-Medical Waste Ash Concrete Cube.

2. Graph (2) shows the Compression Between Conventional Concrete Cube with 20% Add Bio-Medical Waste Ash Concrete Cube.

3. Graph (3) shows the Compression Between Conventional Concrete Cube with 25% Add Bio-Medical Waste Ash Concrete Cube.

4. Graph (4) shows the Compression Between Conventional Concrete Cube with 15%, 20% and 25% Add Bio-Medical Waste Ash Concrete Cube

CONCLUSION

On the basis of result obtained during the experimental investigation, following conclusion are drawn

(i) Workability decreased as the replacement level increased while maintaining a constant superplasticizer dose of 0.6%.

(ii) The density of fresh concrete experienced a slight decrease with higher replacement levels.

(iii) Concrete made with biomedical waste ash exhibited higher compressive strength compared to conventional concrete up to a replacement level of 7.5%.

(iv) Up to a 10% replacement level, the compressive strength of concrete incorporating biomedical waste ash is comparable to that of conventional concrete.

(v) Based on the laboratory investigation of green concrete incorporating biomedical waste ash as a partial replacement for cement, it is noted that the waste can be effectively utilized in new concrete with an optimal dosage of 3%. At this specified dosage level and under standard curing conditions, the reduction in compressive strength is minimal (26%) compared to other curing durations and waste dosages. Consequently, it is inferred that biomedical waste ash exhibits promising potential for integration into fresh concrete as a partial substitute for cement, thereby contributing to waste management while serving as an alternative cementitious material

REFERENCE

- [1] Uma Devi., Prof. R. Rathig.(March 2019)“Effective Utilization of Bio-Medical Waste in Construction Industry”. International Journal of Innovative Research in Science Engineering . Vol. 8, Issue 3, 2319-8753
- [2] Ghulam Mustafa Khazada , Bashir Ahmed Memon.(JAN–JUN, 2020) “Effect of Bio-Medical Waste on Compressive Strength of Concrete Cylinders”. Quest Reserch Journal, VOL. 18, NO. 1, PP. 29–35
- [3] Udit Kumar, Vikas Srivastava, Amit Kumar Singh .(June 2016)“Suitability of Biomedical Waste Ash in Concrete”. International Journal of Engineering and Technical Research. Volume-5, Issue-2, 2321-0869
- [4] Sathvik S, Suchith. S, Edwin.(April 2019)” Partial Replacement of Biomedical Waste ASH in Concrete”. International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJTEE). Volume-8, Issue- 6S4, 2278-3075.
- [5] Tina Maria Sunny(2018)” Use of biomedical plastic waste in bituminous road construction”. International Journal of Current Engineering And Scientific Research (IJCESR). VOLUME-5, ISSUE-4, 2394-0697